

D4.2 Functional Safety

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Executive summary

This deliverable includes the requirements in order to develop a BMS according to the automotive ISO 26262 (Functional safety) standard.

It is focused on concept phase development activities (Item definition, Hazard and Risk Assessment and Functional Safety Concept) for the BMS item.

A preliminary technical Safety Concept derived from the Functional Safety Concept is defined in order to guide the following BMS development phases.

A summary of the ISO 26262 sections related to process and activities is also provided, highlighting key aspects.

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List of abbreviations

ASIL	<i>Automotive Safety Integrity Level</i>
BMC	<i>Battery Management Controller</i>
BMS	<i>Battery Management System</i>
BP	<i>Battery Packs</i>
CMC	<i>Cell Module Controller</i>
EV	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
FMEA	<i>Failure Mode and Effects Analysis</i>
FTA	<i>Fault Tree Analysis</i>
FuSa	<i>Functional Safety</i>
FXXX	<i>Item function ID (XXX is replaced by numbers)</i>
GXXX	<i>Safety Goal ID (XXX is replaced by numbers)</i>
HXXX	<i>Hazard Identification number (XXX is replaced by numbers)</i>
LFM	<i>Latent-Fault Metric</i>
PMHF	<i>Probabilistic Metric for random Hardware Failures</i>
SM	<i>Identify requirements implementing Safety Mechanisms</i>
SCM	<i>Smart Cell Manager</i>
SM	<i>Identify requirements implementing Safety Mechanisms</i>
SPFM	<i>Single-Point Fault Metric</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide a guideline for the development of the MARBEL BMS considering ISO 26262 Standard[1].

The scope of the ISO 26262 is to mitigate the harm to the driver caused by a malfunction of the Electrical and Electronic systems that are present in nowadays vehicles. The ISO 26262 standard addresses the harm reduction in two main aspects:

1. Product related aspects and,
2. Process related aspects.

This document will cover the product related aspects by describing the Item (1 ITEM DESCRIPTION), performing the HARA (2. HAZARD ANALYSIS AND RISK ASSESSMENT), developing the Safety Goals and functional safety requirements (3 FUNCTIONAL SAFETY REQUIREMENTS) and describing a top level Technical Safety Concept (4. TECHNICAL SAFETY CONCEPT).

Process related aspects will be mentioned in Table 11: Technical Safety Requirements.

1. SAFETY ANALYSIS

According to ISO 26262 a safety analysis - Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) – has been performed in order to identify and provide a rationale on of the safety mechanisms at proposed technical safety concept level. Further refinement of this analysis as well as additional safety analyses shall be done during further development phases (Table 11: Technical Safety Requirements).

ISO 26262 PROCESS GUIDELINE FOR ASIL-D DEVELOPMENTS)

The FTA determines the possible causes, analyzing the possible combinations of multiple faults and events or situations, which may lead to a hazard. FTA was performed one for each Safety Goal identified in Table 4.

The identified causes that may violate the safety goal are directly related to the malfunction of the technical safety requirements identified by MARBEL. In order to avoid a Single Point Fault (SPF) on the FTA the respective safety mechanisms have been identified.

2. SAFETY ANALYSIS

2.1 Item Definition

The item considered as BMS include the ECU to control the MARBEL Battery Pack (Cell Module controllers and Battery Management Controller) as well as the switching elements and control to allow the serial/parallel connection of the main battery packs.

Figure 1. Preliminary Item Concept.

2.2 Functions of the Item

Lithium-based batteries require an accurate control and monitoring on their operational conditions in order to avoid safety hazards and optimize their service lifetime.

Therefore, the safety related functions of the BMS could be described as follows:

ID	Name
F001	Monitors the status of the battery
F002	Manages the battery connection matrix (serial/parallel)

Table 1. Safety Functions of the BMS.

3. HAZARD ANALYSIS AND RISK ASSESSMENT

The hazard analysis and risk assessments considers the defined item and its main functions relevant for safety. No safety mechanism implemented already, or that could be implemented in the architecture are considered for the analysis.

Hazardous events were identified and defined by evaluating all possible operational and environmental situations. Based on this outcome, each Hazard was classified with a corresponding Safety Integrity Level (ASIL) as defined in ISO26262-3:2018.

The considerations and evaluations performed in the hazard analysis for the intended BMS development are detailed in the hazard identification in Table 2.

Each hazardous event is evaluated according to the following parameters:

1. S: Severity of the hazard (gravity of the potential injuries),
2. E: Exposure to the Hazardous Event (how often this situation may occur) and
3. C: Controllability (in case of the occurrence of the Hazardous Event is the driver able to control it?).

From this analysis, corresponding ASIL classification for each one of the Hazardous Event is obtained as detailed in Table 3.

ID	Location	Road Conditions	Environment	Traffic and People	Item Usage	Malfunctioning Behaviour	Hazard	Potential Effect
HE009	Parking	any	Charging on private parking	any	Unattended charging	[MF001] Does not detect or react (also delayed detection or reaction) to a failure on safety relevant parameters of the battery	[H002] Battery catches fire	Potential damage to the building. Fire may cause injuries to people
HE010	Parking	any	Charging on private parking	any	Charging with driver/passengers on board	[MF001] Does not detect or react (also delayed detection or reaction) to a failure on safety relevant parameters of the battery	[H002] Battery catches fire	Severe injuries due to fire to vehicle occupants
HE011	Parking	any	Charging on public parking	any	Unattended charging	[MF001] Does not detect or react (also delayed detection or reaction) to a failure on safety relevant parameters of the battery	[H002] Battery catches fire	Potential damage to neighbour cars and building. Fire may cause injuries to people
HE012	Parking	any	Charging on public parking	any	Charging with driver/passengers on board	[MF001] Does not detect or react (also delayed detection or reaction) to a failure on safety relevant parameters of the battery	[H002] Battery catches fire	Severe injuries due to fire to vehicle occupants
HE013	Parking	any	Charging on public parking	any	Battery mode selection	[MF003] Failure on battery mode selection provokes a short on battery pack	[H003] Battery is shorted	Potential damage to the car. Potential fire on the battery pack and injuries to passengers/drivers
HE126	Any driving location	Any Road condition	Any environment	any	Change of battery packs configuration from series to parallel	[MF004] Battery packs connected in parallel with different voltages may provoke a fire/damage on BMS system	[H004] Electric damage due to different battery voltages when batteries are connected in parallel	Potential damage on the car. Potential injury due to a malfunction of BMS system

Table 2. Identification of Hazardous Events.

ID	S	Severity Comment	E	Exposure Comment	C.	Controllability Comment	ASIL	Safety Goal	Safe State
HE009	S2	ISO26262-3-Table 1: Severe and life-threatening injuries (survival probable)	E4	ISO26262-3-Table 2: and Table B.2) High probability (considering >10% operating time: one charge/day)	C3	ISO26262-3-Table 3 and Table B.6) Difficult to control or uncontrollable (Less than 90 % of the average drivers or other traffic participants are able to avoid harm: internal failure <u>uncontrollable</u>)	C	[G001] BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters (ASIL D)	Battery disconnected
HE010	S3	ISO26262-3-Table 1: Life-threatening injuries (survival uncertain), fatal injuries	E4	ISO26262-3-Table 2: and Table B.2) High probability (considering >10% operating time: one charge/day)	C3	ISO26262-3-Table 3: and Table B.6) Difficult to control or uncontrollable (Less than 90 % of the average drivers or other traffic participants are able to avoid harm: internal failure <u>uncontrollable</u>)	D	[G001] BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters (ASIL D)	Battery disconnected
HE011	S2	ISO26262-3-Table 1: Severe and life-threatening injuries (survival probable)	E4	ISO26262-3-Table 2: and Table B.2) High probability (considering >10% operating time: one charge/day)	C3	ISO26262-3-Table 3: and Table B.6) Difficult to control or uncontrollable (Less than 90 % of the average drivers or other traffic participants are able to avoid harm: internal failure <u>uncontrollable</u>)	C	[G001] BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters (ASIL D)	Battery disconnected
HE012	S3	ISO26262-3-Table 1: Life-threatening injuries (survival uncertain), fatal injuries	E4	ISO26262-3-Table 2: and Table B.2) High probability (considering >10% operating time: one charge/day)	C3	ISO26262-3-Table 3: and Table B.6) Difficult to control or uncontrollable (Less than 90 % of the average drivers or other traffic participants are able to avoid harm: internal failure <u>uncontrollable</u>)	D	[G001] BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters (ASIL D)	Battery disconnected
HE013	S3	ISO26262-3-Table 1: Life-threatening injuries (survival uncertain), fatal injuries	E4	ISO26262-3-Table 2: and Table B.2) High probability (considering >10% operating time: one charge/day)	C3	ISO26262-3-Table 3: and Table B.6) Difficult to control or uncontrollable (Less than 90 % of the average drivers or other traffic participants are able to avoid harm: internal failure <u>uncontrollable</u>)	D	[G002] BMS shall ensure no short-circuit is done between the negative and positive poles of the battery pack (ASIL D)	Inform of critical event to ECU supervisor
HE126	S2	ISO26262-3-Table 1: Severe and life-threatening injuries (survival probable)	E4	ISO26262-3-Table 2: and Table B.2) High probability (Any condition)	C3	ISO26262-3-Table 3: and Table B.6) Difficult to control or uncontrollable (Less than 90 % of the average drivers or other traffic participants are able to avoid harm: internal failure <u>uncontrollable</u>)	C	[G005] BMS shall ensure that no parallel battery pack connection is allowed in case voltages on battery pack 1 and battery pack 2 are not balanced (ASIL C)	Inform of critical event to ECU supervisor

Table 3. Hazard Classification.

In order to reduce the risk of all possible hazards to a tolerable level, a top-level safety requirement, the safety goal, must be defined for each of the hazardous events. Based on the result of the Hazard analysis the Safety Goals in the project can be summarized as follows:

ID	Name	Safe State	ASIL
G001	BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters	Battery disconnected	D
G002	BMS shall ensure no short-circuit is done between the negative and positive poles of the battery pack	Inform of critical event to ECU supervisor	D
G005	BMS shall ensure that no parallel battery pack connection is allowed in case voltages on battery pack 1 and battery pack 2 are not balanced	Inform of critical event to ECU supervisor	C

Table 4. Safety Goals for BMS.

4. FUNCTIONAL SAFETY REQUIREMENTS

4.1 Requirements Structure

Based on the Safety goals derived from the Hazard Analysis, a preliminary architecture with all safety relevant elements in BMS were identified as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Preliminary System Architecture

Thereafter, all functional safety requirements, including the safety mechanisms to be implemented in the item, needed to fulfil each Safety Goal are defined and allocated to each of the relevant elements.

Figure 3 is the model diagram of primary safety requirements for BMS, in which the contributions to each of the safety goals and safety mechanisms are defined and grouped based on functionality.

Figure 3. Safety Requirements Diagram

4.2 Functional Safety Requirements

All functional safety requirements determined for BMS are described in Table 5 with their corresponding ASIL classification and the allocation to relevant elements.

Note: The number in column N° in Table 5 assigned to each requirement in the table indicates the hierarchy of the requirements structure, where requirement with a second level number (e.i 1.1) are requirement derived from the primary functional safety requirement (e.i 1).

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
1	SR001	BMS shall sense individual cell voltages	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
1.1	SR019	Cell Module Controller 1 shall sense the voltages of each cell included on the Battery pack 1 and transmit those values to BMC	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 1
1.2	SR020	Cell Module Controller 2 shall sense the voltages of each cell included on the Battery pack 2 and transmit those values to BMC	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 2
1.3	SR021	BMC shall receive the cell voltages of the battery packs	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
2	SR002	BMS shall sense temperature of hotspots on cell modules	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
2.1	SR022	Cell Module Controller 1 shall sense the temperature of the hotspots of battery pack 1 and transmit this value to BMC	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 1

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
2.2	SR023	Cell Module Controller 2 shall sense the temperature of the hotspots of battery pack 2 and transmit this value to BMC	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 2
2.3	SR024	BMC shall receive the temperatures from the battery packs hotspots	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
3	SR003	BMC shall sense the current flowing to Battery Pack1	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
4	SR004	BMC shall sense the current flowing to Battery Pack2	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
5	SR005	BMC shall check the safe range of cell voltage (undervoltage and overvoltage)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
6	SR006	BMC shall check overcurrent conditions on any of the battery packs	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
7	SR007	BMS shall check overtemperature conditions on any of the cell modules	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
8	SR008	SM: BMS shall diagnose the correctness of the cell voltage measurement	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2 • BMC
8.1	SR025	SM: Cell Module Controller shall be equipped with diagnostic capabilities to detect internal faults on the voltage measurement	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
8.2	SR026	SM: BMC shall trigger the internal cell module controller diagnostic and recognize any fault affecting voltage measurement detected on the Cell Module Controller	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
9	SR009	SM: BMS shall diagnose the correctness of the cell module temperature measurement	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
9.1	SR027	SM: Cell Module Controller shall be equipped with diagnostic capabilities to detect internal faults on the temperature measurement	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
9.2	SR028	SM: BMC shall trigger the internal cell module controller diagnostic and recognize any fault affecting temperature measurement detected on the Cell Module Controller	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
10	SR010	SM: BMC shall diagnose the correctness of the current measurement	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
11	SR011	SM: If a fault is detected on the cell voltage measurement chain, BMS shall transition to safe state (cut energy flow)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS • DC-Box
11.1	SR029	SM: BMC shall open the contactors in case there is a fault on the cell voltage measurement chain	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
11.2	SR030	SM: BMC shall request DC Box to stop charging if there is a fault on the cell voltage measurement chain	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
12	SR012	SM: If a fault is detected on the cell module temperature measurement chain, BMS shall transition to safe state (cut energy flow)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS • DC-Box
12.1	SR031	SM: BMC shall open the contactors in case there is a fault on the cell module temperature measurement chain	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
12.2	SR032	SM: BMC shall request DC Box to stop charging if there is a fault on the cell module temperature measurement chain	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
13	SR013	SM: If a fault is detected on the battery pack current measurement chain, BMS shall transition to safe state (cut energy flow)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS • DC-Box
13.1	SR033	SM: BMC shall open the contactors in case there is a fault on the battery pack current measurement chain	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
13.2	SR034	SM: BMC shall request DC Box to stop charging if there is a fault on the battery pack current measurement chain	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
14	SR014	If a cell overvoltage or undervoltage event is detected, BMS shall transition to safe state (cut energy flow)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS • DC-Box
14.1	SR037	BMC shall open the contactors in case there a cell overvoltage or undervoltage event is detected	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
14.2	SR038	BMC shall request DC Box to stop charging in case there a cell overvoltage or undervoltage event is detected	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
15	SR015	If a overcurrent event is detected, BMS shall transition to safe state (cut energy flow)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS • DC-Box
15.1	SR039	BMC shall open the contactors in case a overcurrent event is detected	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
15.2	SR040	BMC shall request DC Box to stop charging in case a overcurrent event is detected	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
16	SR135	If an overcurrent event is detected during a battery configuration transition, BMC shall inform through vehicle CAN on a critical overcurrent event	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
17	SR016	If cell module overtemperature event is detected, BMS shall transition to safe state (cut energy flow)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS • DC-Box
17.1	SR041	BMC shall open the contactors in case cell module overtemperature event is detected	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
17.2	SR042	BMC shall request DC Box to stop charging in case cell module overtemperature event is detected	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
18	SR017	BMS shall avoid to short circuit any battery pack	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC • CONTACTORS
19	SR043	SM: BMC shall implement a mechanism to avoid simultaneous close of contactors that can provoke a short-circuit on the battery pack	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
20	SR018	BMS shall implement mechanisms to prevent unauthorized manipulation of the system (either physical manipulation or digital manipulation)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2 • Comm to external management module
20.1	SR044	BMS shall implement a mechanism to prevent unauthorized manipulation of the battery packs or CMC	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
20.2	SR045	BMC shall implement mechanisms to avoid unauthorized manipulation of the SW or HW in all access means (physical or telematic)	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC
20.3	SR046	BMC shall implement protection mechanisms on the communication layer with Cell Module Controllers to avoid unauthorized manipulation of the data flow	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
20.4	SR047	Cell Module Controllers shall implement protection mechanisms on the communication layer with the BMC to avoid unauthorized manipulation of the data flow	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
21	SR035	Contactors shall be open based on BMC request	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• CONTACTORS
22	SR036	DC Box shall follow charging stop request from BMC	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• DC-Box
23	SR105	SM: E2E communications	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC • Cell Module Controller 1 • Cell Module Controller 2
24	SR114	BMS shall measure battery pack voltage	FUNCTIONAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC
25	SR116	BMS shall not change to parallel battery configuration if the difference between battery voltages are above a certain limit	FUNCTIONAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC
26	SR125	SM: BMC shall verify the correctness of the measured battery voltages	FUNCTIONAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC
27	SR134	BMC shall process the request to transition to safe state	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC
28	SR130	SM: BMC shall prevent the processing errors	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC

N°	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
29	SR131	SM: BMC shall diagnose the correctly opening of the contactors	FUNCTIONAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMC

Table 5. Functional Safety Requirements.

5. TECHNICAL SAFETY CONCEPT

5.1 Detailed System Architecture

Considering the Safety goals and their corresponding functional safety requirements, a detailed system architecture is established to provide an in-depth analysis of the system elements functionalities, dependencies and constraints, and thus, to derive the requirements needed for implementation. These requirements are the technical safety requirements.

In order to achieve a flexible BMS system that can adapt to different applications, it is necessary to consider an architecture that allows changing the battery packs connection from series to parallel and vice versa. Additionally, the Safe State of the BMS shall be accomplished by isolating the battery packs from the vehicle, independently of the series or parallel configuration.

The system architecture defined in Figure 4 shows the interaction of all elements in the BMS system to fulfil the above-mentioned scope.

Figure 4. Detailed system architecture with flexible battery configuration.

The dashed line between CMCs and BMC represents a wireless communication path.

K1 and K2 contactors are the main contactors in order to disconnect the battery packs from the vehicle loads or chargers.

K3, K4 and K5 contactors are used in order to switch the battery configuration from series to parallel or vice versa as described in Table 6.

Battery configuration	K3 Contactor	K4 Contactor	K5 Contactor
Series	OPEN	CLOSED	OPEN
Parallel	CLOSED	OPEN	CLOSED

Table 6. Battery Configuration Contactors States.

Considering the architecture on Figure 4, there are different possibilities for ASIL decomposition (according to ISO26262-9), depending on the function split and implementation among architecture elements. In particular, the Item safe state is defined as battery disconnected and this condition can be accomplished by either disconnecting K1 and K2 OR disabling the charging by the DC-Box, next sections discuss the different options, highlighting its advantages and drawbacks. Note, however that those sections are provided as guidance only and the final implementation is responsibility of the BMS designer.

5.1.1 System Architecture Option 1

In this option, the battery disconnection is performed entirely by the BMS.

Following table shows the ASIL classification of BMS, DC-Box, K1 and K2 contactors for Contactor Opening function.

System Element	ASIL Classification
BMS*	ASIL-D
DC-Box*	QM
K1 Contactor	ASIL-B(D) **
K2 Contactor	ASIL-B(D) **

Table 7. Contactor opening Function ASIL classification for Architecture Option 1.

*This ASIL classification is referred only to the Contactor Opening function implemented by the BMS and DC-Box.

** This decomposition assumes that the charge is interrupted with the opening of one of the main contactors (K1 or K2). In order to reach this decomposition independence on the contactor opening function shall be ensured.

ISO26262 understand independence as the absence of common cause of failures.

5.1.2 System Architecture Option 2

In this option, the battery disconnection is shared between the BMS and DC-BOX. DC-BOX internal contactors are requested to be opened by the BMS.

Following table shows the ASIL classification of BMS, DC-Box, K1 and K2 contactors for Contactor Opening function.

System Element	ASIL Classification
BMS*	ASIL-B(D)

System Element	ASIL Classification
DC-Box*	ASIL-B(D)
K1 Contactor	ASIL-A(D) **
K2 Contactor	ASIL-A(D) **

Table 8. Contactor opening Function ASIL classification for Architecture Option 2.

*This ASIL classification is referred only to the Contactor Opening function implemented by the BMS and DC-Box. Independency requirement is partly ensured by the fact that BMS and DC-BOX (independent ECUs) are able to stop charge.

** This decomposition assumes that the charge is interrupted with the opening of one of the main contactors (K1 or K2). In order to reach this decomposition independence on the contactor opening function shall be ensured.

ISO26262 understand independence as the absence of common cause of failures.

5.1.3 ASIL decomposition for battery configuration contactors

For battery configuration contactors, a similar ASIL decomposition related to contactor control functions can be done for G002.

System Element	ASIL Classification
K3 Contactor	ASIL-B(D)
K4 Contactor	ASIL-B(D)
K5 Contactor	ASIL-B(D)

Table 9. Contactor ASIL classification for G002

5.1.4 System Architecture Selection

In this section, the advantages and drawbacks of each architecture options are listed.

Architecture option	Advantages	Drawbacks
Option 1	1) ASIL development is contained in one ECU	1) Higher development process complexity on BMS
Option 2	1) More reliable solution (2 independent ECUs) 2) Development process complexity is reduced	1) ASIL development is needed for 2 ECUs 2) Management of Battery contactors configuration is developed as ASIL-D for BMS (SG2 is ASIL-D)

Table 10. Architecture selection comparison.

Considering the Table 10. Architecture selection comparison.

Option 1 is selected in order to contain the ASIL development on the BMC. This option allows also to commonize the implementation solution for contactor management (Contactor management of K1, K2, K3, K4 and K5 with same ASIL level).

5.2 Technical Safety Requirements

The technical safety requirements derived for MARBEL BMS system are listed in Table 12, including requirements related to the safety mechanisms identified through safety analysis.

Note: The FSR Ref. N° in Table 12 indicates the hierarchy level of the requirements structure with respect to functional safety requirements.

Note: The ASIL level of the high-level technical safety requirements do not consider the decomposition mentioned on 5.1 Detailed System Architecture. The final decision of the ASIL decomposition depends on the BMS designer.

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
1.1.1	SR048	Cell module controller 1 shall acquire all battery cell voltage with a accuracy better than VCellAcc on the range: VCellRange	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
1.1.2	SR049	Cell module controller 1 shall transmit all battery cell voltage to BMC each VCellTR	TECHNICAL	D	REVIEWED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
1.2.1	SR050	Cell module controller 2 shall acquire all battery cell voltage with a accuracy better than VCellAcc on the range: VCellRange	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller
1.2.2	SR051	Cell module controller 2 shall transmit all battery cell voltage to BMC each VCellTR	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller
1.3.1	SR052	BMC shall receive all battery cell voltage from up to two Battery Packs each VCELLTR	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
2.1.1	SR053	Cell module controller shall acquire NTempSen	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
2.1.2	SR054	Cell module controller shall transmit the temperature of the hotspots of battery pack 1 to BMC each TempSenTR	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
2.1.3	SR055	Placement of temperature sensors shall be ensured to be on battery module hotspots. Note: Requirement relevant for design	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Battery Pack 1 : Battery Pack
2.2.1	SR056	Cell module controller shall acquire NTempSen	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
2.2.2	SR057	Cell module controller shall transmit the temperature of the hotspots of battery pack 2 to BMC each TempSenTR	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller
2.2.3	SR058	Placement of temperature sensors shall be ensured to be on battery module hotspots. Note: Requirement relevant for design	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• Battery Pack 2 : Battery Pack
2.3.1	SR059	BMC shall receive all battery pack temperature measurements from up to two Battery Packs each TempSenTR	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
3.1	SR060	BMC shall be able to sense current with an accuracy better than CACC under all operation conditions	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
3.2	SR061	BMC shall sense current with the following timing period: CPER	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
4.1	SR062	BMC shall be able to sense current with an accuracy better than CACC under all operation conditions	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
4.2	SR063	BMC shall sense current with the following timing period: CPER	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
5.1	SR064	BMC shall verify that each measured cell voltage (Vcell_Meas) is inside the safety limits: $V_{cell_sl_min} < V_{cell_Meas} < V_{cell_sl_min}$	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
6.1	SR065	BMC shall verify that each measured currents are below inside the safety limits: $\text{abs}(C_Meas) < C_sl_max$	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	• BMC : BMC
7.1	SR066	BMC shall verify that each battery pack temperature measurements (Temp_meas) are below the safety limits: $\text{Temp_meas} < \text{Temp_meas_sl_max}$	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	• BMC : BMC
8.1.1	SR067	SM: Cell Module Controller shall include sufficient diagnostics on the measurement acquisition and processing to ensure that a deviation on cell voltage measurement able to prevent a detection of cell under or over voltage is detected	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
8.1.2	SR071	SM: Faults on CMC voltage measurement shall be diagnosed inside the following maximum timing: FDTI_Vcell_CMC	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
8.2.1	SR070	SM: BMC shall enable the CMC voltage measurement diagnostics and recognize the possible faults inside the following maximum timing: FDTI_Vcell_BMC	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	• BMC : BMC
8.3	SR069	SM: CMC and BMCs shall be able to detect a fault on the cell voltage measurement inside the defined fault detection time interval: $\text{FDTI_VCell} = \text{FDTI_Vcell_CMC} + \text{FDTI_Vcell_BMC}$	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller • BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
9.1.1	SR073	SM: Cell Module Controller shall include sufficient diagnostics on the measurement acquisition and processing to ensure that a deviation on temperature measurement able to prevent a detection of overtemperature is detected	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
9.1.2	SR074	SM: Faults on CMC voltage measurement shall be diagnosed inside the following maximum timing: FDTI_BPTemp_CMC	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
9.2.1	SR075	SM: BMC shall enable the CMC temperature measurement diagnostics and recognize the possible faults inside the following maximum timing: FDTI_BPTemp_BMC	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
9.3	SR072	SM: CMC and BMCs shall be able to detect a fault on the Battery Pack temperature measurement inside the defined fault detection time interval: $FDTI_BPTemp = FDTI_BPTemp_CMC + FDTI_BPTemp_BMC$	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller • BMC : BMC
10.1	SR076	SM: BMC shall be able to detect a fault on current measurement acquisition able to prevent a detection of overcurrent event.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	• BMC : BMC
10.2	SR077	SM: BMCs shall be able to detect a fault on the current measurement inside the defined fault detection time interval: FDTI_BPCurr	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	• BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
11.1.1	SR078	SM: BMC shall command to open the contactors in less than FRTI_OpenCont_CV due to an error on the cell voltage measurement chain	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
11.2.1	SR079	SM: BMC shall request DCBox to stop charging in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_CV due to an error on the cell voltage measurement chain	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
12.1.1	SR080	SM: BMC shall command to open the contactors in less than FRTI_OpenCont_TS due to an error on the Battery pack temperature measurement chain	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
12.2.1	SR081	SM: BMC shall request DCBox to stop charging in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_TS due to an error on the Battery pack temperature measurement chain	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
13.1.1	SR082	SM: BMC shall command to open the contactors in less than FRTI_OpenCont_CS due to an error on the Battery pack current measurement chain	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
13.2.1	SR083	SM: BMC shall request DCBox to stop charging in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_CS due to an error on the Battery pack current measurement chain	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
14.1.1	SR084	BMC shall command to open the contactors in less than FRTI_OpenCont_COUV due to a Cell Over/Undervoltage	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
14.2.1	SR085	BMC shall request DCBox to stop charging in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_COUV due to a Cell Over/Undervoltage	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
15.1.1	SR086	BMC shall command to open the contactors in less than FRTI_OpenCont_OC due to a Battery pack Overcurrent	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
15.2.1	SR087	BMC shall request DCBox to stop charging in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_OC due to a Battery pack Overcurrent	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
16.1	SR136	BMC shall send an error CAN message when overcurrent is detected during the transition of battery configuration within FRTI_ConfigChangeReq_OC	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
17.1.1	SR088	BMC shall command to open the contactors in less than FRTI_OpenCont_OT due to a Overtemperature event	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
17.2.1	SR089	BMC shall request DCBox to stop charging in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_OT due to a Overtemperature event	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
18.1	SR110	BMC shall avoid simultaneous closing of K5 and K4 contactor	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
18.2	SR111	BMC shall avoid simultaneous closing of K3 and K4 contactor	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
19.1	SR090	SM: BMC shall check K4 contactor command and status before closing K5 contactor	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
19.2	SR112	SM: BMC shall check K4 contactor command and status before closing K3 contactor	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
19.3	SR113	SM: If K4 is closed when "Battery Configuration Request" is parallel, BMC shall avoid Battery Configuration Switch and send error CAN message	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.1.1	SR091	CMC Modules shall include a mechanism of identification: A unique ID shall be stored on a non-volatile memory	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
20.1.2	SR093	In Battery Configuration Mode, the BMC shall read the CMC ID and store this data in a non-volatile memory. This CMC ID data stored on the BMC is also referred as battery pack manufacturing configuration.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.1.3	SR094	Battery pack manufacturing configuration data shall be stored in a non-volatile memory. This data shall be protected from manipulation and shall not be modified unless the battery configuration mode is enabled	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.1.4	SR095	BMC shall read CMC IDs at start-up and compare with the battery pack manufacturing configuration.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
20.1.5	SR096	If BMC detects a discrepancy between CMC IDs and battery pack manufacturing configuration, the BMC shall remain in non-operation (safe state)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.1.6	SR092	BMC Module shall include a battery configuration mode protected by a secured key	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.2.1	SR097	Physical access to HW and SW shall be prevented	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.2.2	SR098	In case there is a communication path from the BMS to an external server, this communication as well as access to this external server shall be secured.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.3.1	SR099	BMC shall secure communication with CMC using at least IntComProt standard. Note: A standard providing higher security is possible.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
20.4.1	SR100	CMC shall secure communication with BMC using at least IntComProt standard. Note: A standard providing higher security is possible.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
21.1	SR101	Contactors shall be able to open under load conditions at least a current above 2 times C_sl_max (>2*C_sl_max)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• K4 Contactor : Contactors • K1 Contactor : Contactors • K3 Contactor : Contactors • K2 Contactor : Contactors • K5 Contactor : Contactors

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
21.2	SR102	Contactors shall be able to open in less than FRTI_OpenCont_CNT even under load conditions at least a current above 2 times C_sl_max (>2*C_sl_max)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K4 Contactor : Contactors • K1 Contactor : Contactors • K3 Contactor : Contactors • K2 Contactor : Contactors • K5 Contactor : Contactors
22.1	SR103	DC Box Contactors shall be able to open under load conditions at least a current above 2 times C_sl_max (>2*C_sl_max)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DC-Box : DCBox
22.2	SR104	DC Box shall be able to open its contactors in less than FRTI_CharStopReq_DCB even under load conditions at least a current above 2 times C_sl_max (>2*C_sl_max). This timing includes the time from BMC command reception to DCBox contactor open.	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DC-Box : DCBox
23.1	SR106	SM: CMC shall protect the send messages to BMC (CRC and alive counter)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
23.2	SR107	SM: BMC shall verified received messages correctness from CMC (CRC and alive counter)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMC : BMC
23.3	SR108	SM: BMC shall protect the send messages to CMC (CRC and alive counter)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G001 (ASIL D) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
23.4	SR109	SM: CMC shall verified received messages correctness from BMC (CRC and alive counter)	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	• CMC2 : Cell Module Controller • CMC1 : Cell Module Controller
23.5	SR135	SM: BMC shall protect the send messages to DC Box (CRC and alive counter) Note: Only applicable for system architecture Option 2	TECHNICAL	B(D)	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D)	
24.1	SR117	BMS shall measure battery pack 1 voltage	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
24.1.1	SR120	BMC shall measure battery pack 1 voltage Ubatt1 with an accuracy better than UbattAcc	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
24.1.2	SR121	BMC shall measure battery pack 1 voltage Ubatt1 each UbattTR	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
24.2	SR118	BMS shall measure battery pack 2 voltage	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
24.2.1	SR122	BMC shall measure battery pack 2 voltage Ubatt2 with an accuracy better than UbattAcc	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
24.2.2	SR123	BMC shall measure battery pack 2 voltage Ubatt2 each UbattTR	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
25.1	SR124	If $ABS(U_{batt1}-U_{batt2}) > U_{Ser2Par_BattDiff}$, BMC shall inhibit the transition to Battery Configuration = Parallel	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC

FSR Ref.	ID	Name	Kind	ASIL	Status	Related Safety Goals	Allocations
25.2	SR128	If transition to Battery Configuration= Parallel is inhibited, BMC shall inform supervisor ECU of this limitation	TECHNICAL	QM	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
26.1	SR126	SM: BMC shall compare Ubatt1 with a redundant measurement of battery pack1 voltage. Note: this can be done using a dual channel measurement or comparing Ubatt1 to the sum of all cell voltages on Battery Pack 1	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
26.2	SR127	SM: BMC shall compare Ubatt2 with a redundant measurement of battery pack2 voltage. Note: this can be done using a dual channel measurement or comparing Ubatt2 to the sum of all cell voltages on Battery Pack 2	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
26.3	SR129	SM: If Battery Voltage measurement verification fails, the BMC shall inform supervisor ECU	TECHNICAL	C	PROPOSED	• G005 (ASIL C)	• BMC : BMC
28.1	SR132	SM: BMC shall implement a diagnostic function in order to prevent processing errors	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC
29.1	SR133	SM: BMC shall monitor the voltage on both side of the contactors	TECHNICAL	D	PROPOSED	• G001 (ASIL D) • G002 (ASIL D)	• BMC : BMC

Table 11. Technical Safety Requirements.

6. ISO 26262 PROCESS GUIDELINE FOR ASIL-D DEVELOPMENTS

This chapter highlight the requirements from the ISO 26262 associated to an ASIL development, note that this is not intended to contain all the requirements on the ISO 26262, but a summary and reference to key parts of the ISO 26262 standard as the safety goals for the BMS is ASIL-D.

6.1 Background:

ASIL-D is the most strict ASIL classification, therefore the requirements related to the product design, product verification and associated processes are the highest possible.

To develop a product with this ASIL level requires a consolidated QM level, an experienced team on safety-products and the highest independence for the verification of the ISO 26262 processes and work products.

This section goes through the different ISO 26262 chapters.

6.2 ISO26262-2 MANAGEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL SAFETY

6.2.1 ISO26262-2.5- Overall Safety Management

Main highlight for this section is that development organization shall be mature in terms of:

- Safety Culture (ISO26262-2.5.4.2)
- Management of anomalies (ISO26262-2.5.4.3)
- Competence management (ISO26262-2.5.4.4)
- Quality management system (ISO26262-2.5.4.5)

6.2.2 ISO26262-2.6- Project Dependent Safety Management

6.2.2.1 Roles and responsibilities in safety management

Relevant people for the development of a Functional Safety-related project shall be identified and have ISO26262 training and experience. Key person is the Safety Manager.

If member qualification is not accomplished at project start, a training plan shall be established

6.2.2.2 Impact Analysis at element level

This activity shall be carried out in case of reuse of a previous development.

6.2.2.3 Safety Plan

This document contains the planning of activities required by the ISO 26262.

6.2.2.4 Safety Case

The safety case is a document that demonstrates with a rationale that the developed product complies with the ISO 26262 and it is safe.

6.2.2.5 Confirmation measures

Confirmation measures include Confirmation Reviews, FuSa Audit and FuSa assessment.

Confirmations shown in the table below are rated as highly recommended (Mandatory) according to the ISO 26262.

Confirmation Measures	Level of independence applies to ASIL-D	Scope
<i>Confirmation Review of the <u>Functional Safety Plan</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety requirements
<i>Confirmation Review of the <u>Functional Safety Concept</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety goals of the item
<i>Confirmation Review of the <u>Technical Safety Concept</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the functional safety requirements from which the technical safety requirements are derived. If ASIL decomposition has been applied to the functional safety concept then the resulting ASIL from the decomposition may be considered.
<i>Confirmation Review of the <u>Integration and Test Strategy</u></i>	I2	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety requirements
<i>Confirmation Review of the <u>Safety Analyses (including dependent failure analysis)</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety requirements
<i>Confirmation Review of the <u>Safety Case</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety requirements
<i><u>Functional Safety Assessment</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety requirements
<i><u>Functional Safety Audit</u></i>	I3	Applies to the highest ASIL among the safety requirements

Table 12. Confirmation measures for an ASIL-D project.

Level of independence I2: The confirmation measure shall be performed by a person who is independent from the team that is responsible for the creation of the considered work product.

Level of independence I3: The confirmation measure shall be performed by a person who is independent, regarding management, resources and release authority, from the department responsible for the creation of the considered work product(s).

6.2.2.6 Release for production

Safety Case and Confirmation measures reports shall be available before the release of production.

6.2.3 ISO26262-2.7- Safety Management regarding Production, Operation, Service and Decommissioning

ISO26262 activities are not finished after Start-of-Production. At the end of the development phase it is necessary to define the responsibilities of the organizations and persons responsible for achieving and maintaining functional safety regarding production, operation, service and decommissioning

6.3 ISO26262-3 CONCEPT PHASE

Activities defined on the concept phase have been carried out and the outcome is included on section 2, 3 and 4 of this deliverable.

6.4 ISO26262-4 PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT: SYSTEM LEVEL

6.4.1 ISO26262-4.6- Technical Safety Concept

An initial version of the technical safety concept is defined in chapter 5. Technical Safety Concept. Further refinement on the technical safety requirements may be needed.

For ASIL decomposition schemes, please check: ISO26262-9:2018, Clause 5.

6.4.1.1 Safety mechanisms

For ASIL-C and ASIL-D developments safety mechanisms shall be specified in order to:

- Prevent faults from being latent (6.4.2.3) →ASIL level for those safety mechanisms shall be at least ASIL-B
- Avoid multiple-point failures (6.4.2.4)

6.4.1.2 Safety Analyses and avoidance of systematic failures

For ASIL-D and ASIL-C Safety goals, both deductive (like FTA) and inductive (FMEA) at system level shall be applied in order to ensure the avoidance of systematic faults.

For ASIL-D both methods (FMEA and FTA) shall be used. Please check ISO26262-9:2018, 8.2.

6.4.1.3 Measures for control of random hardware failures during operation

For ASIL-D, SPFM, LFM and Hardware PMHF analysis shall be performed. At system level, target values for those metrics shall be provided. In this case target metrics are defined in 6.5.3 ISO26262-5.8- Evaluation of Hardware architectural metrics. See Table 14.

6.4.1.4 Verification

The following verification techniques shall be used:

- System design inspection
- Simulation or Prototyping and vehicle tests
- System architectural design analyses

Safety anomalies and incompleteness identified will be reported in accordance with ISO26262-2:2018, 5.4.3.

6.4.2 ISO26262-4.7- System and Item integration and Testing

This section of the ISO 26262 defines the techniques to check the following:

- Appropriate specification of test cases
- Correct implementation of the safety-related functions
- Correct functional performance, accuracy and timing of the safety mechanisms
- Consistent and correct implementation of the external and internal interfaces
- Effectiveness of the hardware fault detection mechanisms
- Robustness of the elements at the hardware-software level

6.5 ISO26262-5 PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT: HW LEVEL

This chapter of the ISO 26262 introduces the requirements associated to the HW development

6.5.1 ISO26262-5.6- Specification of HW Safety Requirements

This ISO 26262 section describes the requirements and characteristics for the HW safety requirements.

For ASIL-C and D development safety mechanisms to avoid latent faults.

6.5.2 ISO26262-5.7- Hardware Design

This ISO 26262 section describes the requirements and characteristics for the HW design, both architectural and detailed design

6.5.2.1 Safety Analyses and avoidance of systematic failures

For ASIL-D and ASIL-C Safety goals, both deductive (like FTA) and inductive (FMEA) at HW level shall be applied in order to ensure the avoidance of systematic faults.

If Independence requirements are derived → Analysis of dependant failures

6.5.2.2 Verification of hardware design

The following verification techniques shall be used:

- HW design inspection
- HW architectural design analyses

6.5.2.3 Production, operation, service and decommissioning

If requirements related to production, operation, service and decommissioning are identified during HW development, it shall be communicated appropriately

6.5.3 ISO26262-5.8- Evaluation of Hardware architectural metrics

HW detailed design shall be evaluated against the following targets defined by the ISO 26262 for :

Analysis item	Target for ASIL-C	Target for ASIL-D
Single Point Fault Metric (SPFM)	≥97%	≥99%
Latent Fault Metric (LFM)	≥80%	≥90%

Table 13. HW Architectural metrics

6.5.4 ISO26262-5.9- Evaluation of safety goals violation due to random hardware failures

HW detailed design shall be evaluated against the following targets defined by the ISO 26262 for :

Analysis item	Target for ASIL-C	Target for ASIL-D
PHMF	≤100FIT	≤10FIT

Table 14. PHMF Target Metrics.

6.5.5 ISO26262-5.10- Hardware integration and verification

This section of the ISO 26262 defines the techniques to check the following:

- Appropriate specification of test cases
- Hardware integration tests to verify the completeness and correctness of the safety mechanisms implementation with respect to the hardware safety requirements
- Correct functional performance, accuracy and timing of the safety mechanisms
- Hardware integration tests against external stresses

6.6 ISO26262-6 PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT: SW LEVEL

This chapter of the ISO 26262 introduces the requirements associated to the SW development

6.6.1 ISO26262-6.5- General topics for the product development at the software level

This section describes general requirements for the SW development of a FuSa-related product. In particular, the existence of coding guidelines

6.6.2 ISO26262-6.6- Specification of software safety requirements

This ISO 26262 section describes the requirements and characteristics for the SW safety requirements.

6.6.3 ISO26262-6.7- Software architectural design

This ISO 26262 section describes the requirements and characteristics for the SW architectural design.

6.6.4 ISO26262-6.8- Software unit design and implementation

This ISO 26262 section describes the requirements and characteristics for the SW unit design and implementation.

6.6.5 ISO26262-6.9- Software unit verification

ISO 26262 covers the following aspects of SW unit verification:

- Methods for software unit verification
- Methods for deriving test cases for software unit testing
- Structural coverage metrics at the software unit level

6.6.6 ISO26262-6.10- Software integration and verification

ISO 26262 covers the following aspects of SW integration and verification:

- Methods for verification of software integration
- Methods for deriving test cases for software integration test
- Structural coverage metrics at the software architectural level

6.6.7 ISO26261-6.11- Testing of the embedded software

ISO 26262 covers the following aspects of SW integration and verification:

- Test environments for conducting the software testing
- Methods for tests of the embedded software
- Methods for deriving test cases for the test of the embedded software

6.7 ISO26262-7 Production, operation, service and decommissioning

In this section, the requirements related to production and after production lifecycle of the FuSa product are detailed. This is out of scope for MARBEL project.

6.8 ISO26262-8 Supporting Processes

This ISO 26262 chapter describes the supporting processes related to the development of an ASIL ECU/System

6.8.1 ISO26262-8.5- Interfaces within distributed developments

This section describes the requirements in case the FuSa system is developed within different companies/organizations. Main document for this is the Development Interface Agreement (DIA), in which the activities developed by the different parties are agreed.

6.8.2 ISO26262-8.6- Specification and management of safety requirements

This section describes the characteristics of the Safety requirements and the way to manage them.

6.8.3 ISO26262-8.7- Configuration management

This section describes the ISO 26262 requirements regarding to Configuration management.

6.8.4 ISO26262-8.9- Verification

This section describes the ISO 26262 requirements regarding to Verification process used in system, HW and SW development phases.

6.8.5 ISO26262-8.10- Documentation management

This section describes the ISO 26262 requirements regarding to Documentation management.

6.8.6 ISO26262-8.11- Confidence in the use of software tools

This ISO 26262 section describes the analysis that shall be done for each SW tool used on a safety project. In case a SW tool qualification is needed, the method to qualify it depends on the ASIL level

6.8.7 ISO26262-8.12- Qualification of software components

This section describes the ISO 26262 requirements regarding to Qualification of SW components not developed according to the ISO 26262.

6.8.8 ISO26262-8.13- Evaluation of hardware elements

This section describes the ISO 26262 requirements regarding to the evaluation of the HW components used in an ISO 26262 development.

6.9 ISO26262-9 ASIL-Oriented Analysis

This chapter describes different aspects related to ASIL classification (decomposition and criteria for coexistence), analysis of dependent failures and general requirements for the Safety Analysis.

6.9.1 ISO26262-9-5 Requirements decomposition with respect to ASIL tailoring (ASIL decomposition)

This section describes the possible ASIL decomposition schemes and ASIL decomposition related requirements. Practical application of this is done on 5.1 Detailed System Architecture.

6.9.2 ISO26262-9-6 Criteria for coexistence of elements

This section describes the requirements related to ASIL classification of elements that contain sub-elements with different ASIL classification.

6.9.3 ISO26262-9-7 Analysis of dependent failures

This section describes the analysis of dependent failures (absence of cascading and common-cause failures).

6.9.4 ISO26262-9-8 Safety analyses

This section describes the common requirements for the safety analysis used on the system, HW and SW development phases.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In Marbel project, Work Package 4 (BMS) this document "Functional safety" provide a guideline for the development of BMS following ISO26262 automotive Functional Safety Standard.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] ISO 26262 – “Road vehicles – Functional Safety” (2018)
- [2] MARBEL Technical Annex

9. ANNEXES

ANNEX A. FTA for Safety Goal G001 - BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters.

ANNEX B. FTA for Safety Goal G002 - BMS shall ensure no short-circuit is done between the negative and positive poles of the battery pack.

ANNEX C. FTA for Safety Goal G005 - BMS shall ensure that no parallel battery pack connection is allowed in case voltages on battery pack 1 and battery pack 2 are not balanced.

ANNEX A. FTA for Safety Goal G001 - BMS shall monitor battery pack safety relevant parameters.

The following Figure 5 to Figure 10 shows the FTA developed for the violation of the SG1, it means, the malfunctions that have to occur in the system. In these conditions the BMS will not be ensured or prevented from the hazard “[H002] Battery catches fire” §3

Figure 5. FTA for Safety Goal G001 – Part 1 of 5

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Figure 6. FTA for Safety Goal G001 – Part 2 of 5

Figure 7. FTA for Safety Goal G001 – Part 3 of 5

Figure 8. FTA for Safety Goal G001 – Part 4 of 5

Figure 9. FTA for Safety Goal G001 – Part 5 of 5

Figure 10. FTA for SAFE STATE

ANNEX B. FTA for Safety Goal G002 - BMS shall ensure no short-circuit is done between the negative and positive poles of the battery pack.

The following Figure 11 shows the combinations of faults that must occur for a short circuit in the poles of the battery pack. In these conditions the BMS will not be ensured or prevented from the hazard “[H003] Battery is shorted” §3

Figure 11. FTA for Safety Goal G002

ANNEX C. FTA for Safety Goal G005 - BMS shall ensure that no parallel battery pack connection is allowed in case voltages on battery pack 1 and battery pack 2 are not balanced.

The following Figure 12 shows the combinations of faults that must occur for an improper battery parallel configuration. In these conditions the BMS will not be ensured or prevented from the hazard “[H004] Electric damage due to different battery voltages when batteries are connected in parallel” §3.

Figure 12. FTA for Safety Goal G005